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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND APPROACHES OF TEACHERS IN TEACHING LEARNERS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

Laarni A. Tabora

Benguet State University – Buguias Campus

Abstract.

Globally, inclusive education has become a cornerstone of educational reforms. This study examines the challenges encountered by the teachers, and the approaches they employ in teaching learners with special needs mixed in a regular classroom, in one of the big school in the district of Buguias. Using a qualitative design, the research employed pure qualitative interviews conducted among teachers teaching LSEs in a regular classroom. Findings show that the school strive to foster inclusivity but face barriers such as insufficient time in preparing differentiated activities, limited parental engagement, lack of training and support, diverse learning educational need cases, and unreceptive learners. Effective approaches are provision of simplified activities, initiation of differentiated instruction, encourage collaborative learning, coordination with co-teachers, and parent-teachers conference.

Keywords: inclusive, learners with special needs (LSEs), challenges, approaches

1.0 Introduction

Inclusive education extends beyond providing access to schooling; it promotes equity, diversity, and the recognition of every learner's unique strengths and challenges (Roy & Swargiary, 2023). In the Philippines, Republic Act No. 11650 or the Inclusive Education Act of 2022 ensures that learners with disabilities have equitable access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities. The law also urges educational institutions to accommodate diverse learner needs through inclusive facilities, flexible schedules, and supportive services.

Despite these provisions, implementing inclusive education remains challenging. Teachers often face difficulties such as rigid curricula, inadequate preparation, limited resources, and insufficient institutional support (Priya, 2016; Nwoko et al., 2022; Materechera, 2020). Common issues also include large class sizes, minimal parental involvement, and the absence of assistive materials and adaptive infrastructure (Sumayang et al., 2022; Traya & Lopez, 2023; Mokalleng & Mowes, 2020).

Nevertheless, studies highlight strategies that help address these barriers. Early and continuous training fosters positive teacher attitudes toward inclusion (Carter et al., 2022; Cabañero, 2023; Quinones, 2022), while collaboration among teachers, parents, and administrators strengthens instructional effectiveness (Alido et al., 2023; Beltran et al., 2025). Moreover, adapting instruction and teaching styles is vital in meeting diverse learner needs (Traya & Lopez, 2023).

This study explores the specific challenges teachers face in handling learners with special educational needs (LSEs) in regular classrooms and identifies the strategies they employ to address

them. By offering localized insights, it aims to inform best practices, guide teacher training programs, and enhance support systems for inclusive education.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, which, according to Creswell (2015), seeks to explore and understand the meanings individuals or groups attribute to a social or human phenomenon. Through interviews, this approach allowed the researcher to gain deeper insights into teachers' experiences and perspectives.

2.2 Participants and Sampling Technique

Homogeneous purposive sampling was used to select participants. As defined by Makwana et al. (2023), this non-random method involves selecting individuals with specific knowledge or experience relevant to the research focus. Seven (7) teachers handling learners with special educational needs (LSEs) in regular classrooms were chosen based on their expertise and willingness to participate (Etikan et al., 2016).

2.3 Research Instrument

A researcher-made interview guide served as the main instrument. It provided a flexible framework that encouraged open discussion and allowed participants to elaborate on their experiences (Marie-Lou et al., 2011).

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first secured approval from the adviser and the school principal of Loo National High School. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they understood the study's purpose and confidentiality provisions. Individual face-to-face interviews were then conducted at convenient times, with participants' permission to record. Field notes supplemented the recordings to capture additional insights.

2.5 Data Analysis Procedure

Interviews were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and meanings (Crosley, 2021). Inductive coding was applied, allowing themes to emerge directly from the data. These were later evaluated and substantiated with related literature to strengthen the findings.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and participant autonomy were strictly observed. Participants were assured of anonymity, and all personal information and audio recordings were securely handled. As emphasized by Bos (2020), confidentiality safeguards participants' privacy and prevents misuse or unauthorized disclosure of data.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the themes drawn out from the experiences of teachers concerning the challenges they encounter in teaching LSEs in a regular classroom, likewise, the approaches they employ.

3.1 Challenges Encountered by Teachers

Insufficient Time in Preparing Differentiated Activities

Teachers reported that preparing individualized activities for LSEs is time-consuming, especially when handling several students with special needs in large classes. Participant 1 shared that it is difficult to meet diverse learning needs, while Participant 5 expressed guilt over not giving enough attention due to time constraints. Participant 7 emphasized that inclusive education policies exist without adequate support or materials. This lack of time, resources, and assistive materials hinders inclusive implementation (Alduais & Deng, 2022).

Limited Parental Engagement

Teachers also faced challenges in communicating with parents who had differing views on support approaches. Participant 3 noted that misunderstandings often occur and that some parents rarely attend meetings about their child's behavior, limiting collaborative efforts to support LSEs.

Lack of Training and Support

Most participants admitted lacking proper training to teach LSEs effectively. Participant 4 said it is difficult without specialized knowledge, while Participant 6 noted that this work requires additional expertise. Studies confirm that inadequate training and resources impede teachers' ability to manage LSEs (Nwoko et al., 2022; Cabañero, 2023; Quinones, 2022).

Diverse Learning Needs

Teachers struggled with the wide range of learning difficulties in one classroom. Participant 2 cited problems like poor word recognition and comprehension, while others mentioned short attention spans and disruptive behaviors (P3, P5). Addressing these varied cases simultaneously poses significant instructional challenges.

Unreceptive Learners

Some LSEs were unresponsive or resistant to activities. Participant 7 shared that certain learners refused to communicate or participate, while Participant 6 noted that low self-esteem hinders class involvement. Others preferred isolation during group activities (P4), making engagement difficult.

3.2 Approaches Employed by Teachers

Provision of Simplified Activities

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Teachers simplified lessons and created individualized activities to match each learner's capacity. Participant 1 emphasized tailoring activities based on observation, while Participant 4 prepared tasks suitable to each learner's level. Simplified explanations and one-on-one discussions were common strategies.

Initiation of Differentiated Instruction

Participants used various instructional methods depending on learners' needs and languages. Participant 5 differentiated lessons for learners who understood English or Kankana-ey, while Participant 7 provided oral instructions and extended reviews for those with reading difficulties. Shorter, repetitive activities were also applied to ensure understanding (P3).

Encouraging Collaborative Learning

Teachers promoted group work and peer assistance to foster inclusion. Participant 2 grouped LSEs with fast learners, while Participant 3 found that peer teaching improved understanding. Such collaboration enhances socialization and acceptance among learners (Salend, 2015; Alido et al., 2023).

Coordination with Co-Teachers

Teachers collaborated with colleagues to share observations and strategies for LSEs. Participant 4 highlighted the importance of conferencing to plan appropriate interventions. Collaboration fosters creativity, accountability, and morale in inclusive settings (Ramberg & Watkins, 2020; Vetoniemi & Karna, 2021).

Parent-Teacher Conferences

Maintaining open communication with parents helped monitor and support learners' progress. Participant 6 conducted conferences after PTA meetings to discuss children's development. Effective parent-teacher collaboration enhances support systems for LSEs (Beltran et al., 2025).

4.0 Conclusion

The primary concern of teachers in handling learners with special educational needs (LSEs) in regular classrooms is their lack of training in this specialized area. Without proper orientation and preparation, they struggle to address the diverse needs of these learners. Other challenges include insufficient time to prepare differentiated activities, limited parental involvement, varied learning needs, and unreceptive learners. To address these, teachers employ strategies such as providing simplified activities, implementing differentiated instruction, encouraging collaborative learning, coordinating with co-teachers, and conducting parent-teacher conferences. It is recommended to strengthen parental engagement and sustain teachers' professional growth through continuous in-service training and seminar-workshops on inclusive practices. Furthermore, the Department of Education should extend support by providing specialized learning materials, technical assistance, and capacity-building programs to better equip teachers in managing LSEs in regular classrooms.

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